

THE MODERN METHODS OF TEACHING ENGLISH

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Abstract: In many parts of the world, there is a growing interest in modern methods of teaching English, the question of how to do it - how the curriculum, subject, topic and methodology should differ from the previously developed familiar norms gives birth. Much has been written on traditional English teaching and there is a growing body of knowledge about modern methods of teaching English. Many books and articles have been written to draw attention to this topic today. The use of innovations and new pedagogical technologies is yielding good results. This article discusses several methods and types of teaching.

Keywords: Teaching methods, innovations, methodology, skills, Dialogical speech, reading strategies

The growing interest in many parts of the world in Modern Methods of teaching English brings with it the question of how it should be done – how curriculum, subject, matter, and methodology should differ from the familiar norms developed in the past. A lot has been written on traditional teaching English, and until recently, the demand for the information on Modern Methods of Teaching English has been limited. Nowadays many books and articles are written to attract attention to this point [5]. In planning curricular and methods it has been suggested that an understanding of Students and their needs, interest, abilities, likes, dislikes, and developmental status should take precedence over other considerations.

Known to us, using innovations and new pedagogical technologies are resulting well. Sometimes using same styles in teaching language may let go down interests of student to language. We advise some types of teaching in use, not to go down interest to foreign language.

For instance: 1. Dialogical speech- in this way students have a talk each other by creative approach. “Modern Methodology of Teaching English puts Speaking in

Dialogues in the first place for developing speaking skills [6]. These skills can be trained with various teaching aids, including texts of fiction. Such dialogues give

an opportunity to avoid traditional rendering of the texts and turn them into living English speech”. More than that, all the vocabulary is remembered much better. In dialogues, students train in fluency, quick reaction, acting skills and, of course, grammatical correctness.

2. Learning English through the watching movies. Nowadays, teachers take into consideration students’ demands for watching real movie stories together with reading books, magazines and newspapers. Because, as it is known not only printed materials can serve as a great source of teaching but also songs and movies play a key role in learning foreign languages.

3. Understanding by listening - by these way students can improve speech skills. Listening is a receptive form of speech activity. Comprehension of speech while listening mainly based on auditory feelings. By perceiving, reproduce what we hear, in the form of inwardly speech. Listening comprehension is impossible without working of speech motor analyzer [4]. Of course internal speaking requires ability to speak in this language. Understanding of sounding speech, in the moment of comprehension, is accompanied by intellectual activity, which includes recognizing of speech means and interpretation of the content.

And it is cost to mention that the main approach for studying foreign languages is CLT (Communicative Language Teaching). Communication skills are the abilities that enable you to receive and convey all kinds of information. There are several different types of communication, such as: written, verbal, nonverbal, visual [7].

To conclude the key strategies for teaching English classes are probably developing a positive and collaborative working atmosphere and providing a variety of work suitable for different levels. We have to say, that practically it is impossible to use one method or approach solely when aiming to teach a second language successfully. Lessons should be designed with effective methods of teaching. In this way we’ll get our goals in teaching successfully.

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